

Studies on Quinazol-2,4-diones

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Several quinazol-2,4-diones have been synthesised and their UV and IR spectra studied.

A quinazoline base¹, isolated in our laboratory, on oxidative degradation yielded several products, one of which appeared to be 1-phenyl-7-hydroxyquinazol-2,4-dione. With a view to confirming its structure, an attempt was made to synthesise this compound, but without any promising results. It was therefore intended to study the synthesis of quinazol-2,4-diones where the phenyl nucleus was unsubstituted. The object is to find out the role of phenolic hydroxyl in these syntheses and to see whether this hydroxyl creates any difficulties in the cyclisation of diphenylamines with urethane or its derivatives to quinazol-2,4-diones.

Several such diones have been prepared. It has been observed that the aforesaid cyclisation readily proceeds to the desired systems. These facts obviously conclude that the phenolic hydroxyl in 7-position does hinder the desired cyclisation. The quinazoline compounds, thus synthesised, are described in this communication along with their spectral analyses (both ultraviolet and infrared). Of the five compounds, (IV) and (V) are new and thus their synthesis has been achieved for the first time. The preparation of a few more quinazol-2,4-diones with substitution in the phenyl moiety is in progress, details of which will constitute the subject matter of a future communication.

- (I): $R_1 = R_2 = H$; quinazol-2,4-dione.
 (II): $R_1 = Me$; $R_2 = H$; *N*¹-methylquinazol-2,4-dione.
 (III): $R_1 = R_2 = Me$; *N*¹*N*³-dimethyl „ „
 (IV): $R_1 = Ph$; $R_2 = H$; *N*¹-phenyl „ „
 (V): $R_1 = Ph$; $R_2 = Me$; *N*¹-phenyl-*N*³-methyl- „ „

1. Chatterjee (Mrs.) and Roy, Hand Book of International Congress, Australia, Symposium on the Chemistry of Natural Products (under the auspices of International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry), 1960, p. 12.

The compounds (I—III) have been prepared according to the methods described in the literature²⁻⁴. Compound (III) was synthesised, using an earlier method⁴ with some modifications (vide Experimental). Synthesis of compound (IV) was achieved by condensing *N*-phenylanthranilic ester with urothane. Subsequent treatment of (IV) with methyl iodide in methanolic alkali at reflux temperature yielded compound (V).

TABLE I

Compound.	M.P.	Solubility in ethanol.	U.V. peaks.	I. R. peaks (in cm^{-1}).
1. Quinazol-2,4-dione (QD)*	354°	Sparingly soluble	218 m μ (4.69)** 311 (3.70)	3148,3040,1700,1665, 1615,1509,759.
2. <i>N</i> -Methyl-QD	265°	Moderately ,,	220 (4.64) 313 (3.63)	3150,3040,1710,1665, 1610,1507,760.
3. <i>N</i> ¹ <i>N</i> ³ -Dimethyl-QD	165°	Fairly ,,	220 (4.70) 312 (3.63)	1700,1660,1615,1500, 757.
4. <i>N</i> ¹ -Phenyl-QD	301-302°	Sparingly ,,	219 (4.67) 313 (3.66)	3140,1710,1690,1610, 1502,760.
5. <i>N</i> ¹ -Phenyl- <i>N</i> ³ -methyl-QD	234°	Moderately ,,	219 (4.70) 313 (3.66)	1707,1668,1610,1500, 760.

*QD stands for quinazol-2,4-dione.

**Figures in parentheses refer to $\log \epsilon$ values.

The quinazol-2,4-dione derivatives are characterised by their marked insolubility in usual organic solvents. It is shown in Table I that alkyl at *N*¹ and *N*³ increases the solubility. Phenyl substitution tends to increase the solubility of the compounds, but not to the same degree as that of an alkyl group.

The IR data of all the compounds were studied in Nujol mull and KBr pellet and these were found to be in better agreement with the results of Culbertson and his collaborators² than those of Randall *et al.*⁵ The peaks (at 1658 to 1668 cm^{-1} and at 1700 to 1715 cm^{-1}) obtained for the carbonyl functions (at 2- and 4-positions) were fairly strong for all the compounds. A little shift was observed in the position of the carbonyl band at C₂ for compounds (I), (II), and (IV), which appears to be due to hydrogen bonding with hydrogen at *N*³. The absorptions for the double bonds between 1490 and 1508 cm^{-1} and 1595 and 1610 cm^{-1} were very weak in each case. At longer wave lengths, a sharp absorption band, characteristic for the *ortho*-substituted phenyl group, is discernible between 758 and 765 cm^{-1} , a result which is in good agreement with the values obtained by Whiffen and Thompson⁷ and by Culbertson *et al.*⁵ The band at 1575 to 1585 cm^{-1} for conjugated phenyl rings was, however, found missing in the spectra of all these compounds.

2. Lange and Sheibley, "Organic Syntheses", Coll. Vol. II, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, N. Y., 1947, p. 79.

3. Wang and Christenson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 71, 1440.

4. Abt, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1889, ii, 39, 148.

5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 4834.

6. "Infrared Determination of Organic Structures", D. Van Nostrand Co., Inc., New York, N. Y., 1949.

7. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 268.

The UV spectra of the compounds were examined in spectral alcohol. Two distinct peaks were discernible in the regions of 217-219 $m\mu$ and 312-315 $m\mu$ along with a shoulder in the region of 240-245 $m\mu$. The UV curves are shown in Fig. 1. The λ_{max} values of these compounds remained unchanged in acid (0.05*N*-HCl) and alkali (0.05 *N*-NaOH) media.

FIG. 1

1. Quinazol-2,4-dione.
2. *N*¹-Methylquinazol-2,4-dione.
3. *N*¹*N*³-Dimethylquinazol-2,4-dione.
4. *N*¹-Phenylquinazol-2,4-dione.
5. *N*¹-Phenyl-*N*³-methylquinazol-2,4-dione.

EXPERIMENTAL

Quinazol-2,4-dione (I) and *N*¹-methylquinazol-2,4-dione (II) were synthesized by following the methods of Lango and Sheibley² and Wang and Christensen³ respectively.

*N*¹*N*³-Dimethylquinazol-2,4-dione (III).—Compound (II) (1g.), suspended in 2.8% methanolic NaOH solution (10 ml), was refluxed with methyl iodide (0.5 ml) for

3 hrs. The methanol was evaporated, diluted with water, and filtered. The residue was washed with water and dried. The white solid, thus obtained, was crystallised from boiling ethanol in fine needles, m. p. 165°, yield 85%. (Found: C, 63.11; H, 5.27; N, 14.83. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires C, 63.15; H, 5.26; N, 14.79%).

*N*¹-Phenylquinazol-2,4-dione (IV).—A mixture of ethyl *N*-phenylanthranilate (4 g.) and urethane (4.5 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 180-200° for 2 hrs. and then at 200-220° for another hour. The reaction product, which was a solid mass, was washed with boiling water, dissolved in a hot solution of NaOH (conc.), and filtered. The clear filtrate of the sodio-salt was acidified with (1:1) H_2SO_4 when a white precipitate of *N*¹-phenylquinazol-2,4-dione appeared. This was filtered and the residue was washed with water, dried, and then crystallised repeatedly from boiling ethanol in flakes, m.p. 301-302°, yield 80%. (Found: C, 70.98; H, 4.26; N, 11.61. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires C, 70.6; H, 4.2; N, 11.8%).

*N*¹-Phenyl-*N*³-methylquinazol-2,4-dione (V).—The diketone (IV) (1.2 g.), suspended in 2.8% methanolic NaOH solution (15 ml), was refluxed with methyl iodide (0.8 ml) for 3 hrs. The methanol was evaporated, the residue diluted with water, and filtered. The residue was washed with water and dried. The white solid thus obtained was crystallised from boiling ethanol in fine needles, m.p. 234°, yield 85%. (Found: C, 71.40; H, 4.78; N, 10.82. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires C, 71.43; H, 4.76; N, 11.11%).

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